

However, the conventional reactive media in PRBs such as zero valent ions and zeolite are quite expensive and associated with several issues including non-availability for frequent use [4].

The application of PRBs to treat the groundwater contaminated with landfill-leachate commenced recently. The above-mentioned conventional reactive materials may not have the potential to treat some contaminants in the landfill-leachate. Hence, the experiments on low-cost and readily available reactive materials targeting the contaminants found in landfill-leachate is a timely need [6].

Building waste is a controversial solid waste due to the lack of disposal sites. They are made of a number of chemical compounds, which may have the treatment potential for heavy metals. The usage of the building wastes in PRB walls are very few in the past literature. Therefore, conducting batch sorption experiments using these building wastes are very significant. The building wastes are abundant in the present construction-oriented world. According to the past studies, the building wastes such as bricks, roofs, timber etc. have good adsorption capacities. Dewatered Alum Sludge (DAS) has shown a considerable treatment potential for landfill-leachate [5].

In order to maintain the cost effectiveness, low-cost materials should be used as the reactive media in PRBs. The reactive materials that are used in the PRBs should be readily available because the reactive materials inside PRBs have to be replaced when the efficiency of treatment starts decreasing [13]. Batch experiments are described to screen and select the appropriate materials for use in PRB design trenches [15].

Hence, the aim of this study was to investigate the heavy metals treatment potentials of building wastes and DAS using batch sorption experiments. The objectives were to determine the influences of adsorbent dosage and contact time for the adsorption of heavy metals on each of selected reactive materials and to obtain the optimal adsorption capacity of each of selected reactive materials for different types of heavy metals.

2. Literature Review

According to the literature review, many researchers have done batch sorption

experiments using different reactive materials. Al-Salihy, et al. [2] conducted batch sorption experiments with 'rice husk', and he proved that rice husk, which is low-cost, was considerably efficient for the removal of Cd (II) from a solution where the adsorption processes were well fitted with Freundlich isotherm. BULUT Yasemin [3] conducted batch and column sorption studies using 'saw dust', and he concluded that the saw dust of walnut could be a good adsorbent for the metal ions like Pb (II) and Cd (II) from aqueous solution, and the observed trend was $Pb(II) \approx Cd(II) > Ni(II)$. Etorki, et al. [8] stated that, 'Fava beans' is a good adsorbent material for removal of Pb (II), Cd (II) and Zn (II) ions from aqueous solutions and wastewater samples. The adsorption characteristics of the above study have fitted well with the Langmuir isotherm. Another set of batch experiment has been carried out using 'Coconut husk' as adsorbent by Emoruwa & Agbozu [8]. Finally, they concluded that the adsorption efficiency increased with initial metal ion concentration and the trend was $Cr > Cu > Cd > Fe > Pb$.

Similarly, the past research shows that washed quarry dust (WQD), fly ash, red sand, bio char etc. showed good performances in removing heavy metals from aqueous solutions [5].

Concrete has superplasticizers, z-potentials, admixtures, pigments, fibers and aggregates, which are bound together having a high adsorption rate. Reinforcement has iron oxides, which are having higher rates of adsorbing heavy metal elements. Bricks have a major amount of clay. Clay has some minerals that can remove high concentration of Pb^{2+} [11]. Cement and sand mortar have fly ash, ground granulated blast furnace slag having high capacities in removing particles from liquid solutions. Sand is having PCE and BNS superplasticizers with different fineness and compositions, which have considerable adsorption rates. Especially, ceramic tiles have clay sized crystals of minerals such as quartz and carbonates possessing higher rates of removing heavy metals from aqueous solutions [11].

DAS which is a waste discharged from water treatment plants, have a good wastewater treatment potential [5].

Figure 9 - Heavy metals removal by CW in the adsorption isotherm experiments

Figure 10 - Heavy metals removal by DAS in the adsorption isotherm experiments

Figure 11 - Heavy metals removal by RW in the adsorption isotherm experiments

Table 4 - Optimum mass for each reactive material

Reactive material	Optimum mass (g)
DAS	15
FW	20
BW	15
RW	15
CW	15

Figure 15 depicts the removal efficiency of each heavy metal by each adsorbent at the optimum mass. Table 5 depicts the reactive materials best

suitable for the removal of different types of heavy metals at the optimum adsorbent masses.

Figure 12 - Variation of pH in the influent and supernatants for the adsorption isotherm experiments

Figure 13 - Variation of ORP in the influent and supernatants for the adsorption isotherm experiments

Figure 14 - Variation of Conductivity in the influent and supernatants for the adsorption isotherm experiments

Table 5 shows the best treated heavy metal by each reactive material with their respective

of 461.1 mg/g. The removal efficiencies of Fe, Pb and Cd by all the tested reactive materials were comparatively higher than those of other heavy metals. The application of these waste materials as reactive materials in PRBs would be a temporary solution for the disposal issue of them. However, the long-term operation of these materials inside PRBs would make them no longer suitable as a reactive material. Then, they have to be replaced. Hence, further experiments are suggested to investigate their longevity as well as how to improve the longevity to decrease the frequency of replacements. Further, investigations on the recovery of heavy metals from the reactive materials would also be essential. It is also recommended to check whether there is a possibility of releasing Al into the solution from the adsorbent, DAS as Al is a health concern.

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